

Systematic Review of Users' Satisfaction with Housing Schemes

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Abstract

This study aims to systematically review global literature on residents' satisfaction with housing schemes, identifying key factors influencing satisfaction such as design, socio-economic conditions, infrastructure, amenities, and policy frameworks. Employing the PRISMA protocol, the study ensures methodological rigour through structured data search, screening, and quality appraisal. A comprehensive search of databases including Scopus and JSTOR covered peer-reviewed and grey literature published between 2016 and 2025. Inclusion followed the PICO framework, focusing on public housing residents and outcomes linked to housing quality, services, and resident perceptions. The final selection comprised 18 high-quality studies. Data were extracted and synthesised thematically using a narrative approach, revealing key trends, regional disparities, and best practices to guide future housing policy and resident-focused development strategies. The reviewed studies collectively examine residential satisfaction across diverse housing settings, highlighting the roles of design quality, social environment, and policy effectiveness. Satisfaction is shaped by physical attributes like space and infrastructure, social interactions, community engagement, and subjective perceptions. In subsidised and older neighbourhoods, features such as fitness facilities, community bonds, and participatory governance enhance satisfaction. Policies directly providing housing, especially public rental options, tend to yield higher satisfaction than allowances. Design aspects such as spatial layout, ventilation, and eco-friendly features further influence contentment. In developing regions like Nigeria, implementation gaps and urban planning challenges reduce effectiveness. Overall, inclusive design, community integration, responsive policies, and sustainable infrastructure are key to improving residential experiences and well-being.

Keywords: Residents' satisfaction, Housing schemes, Infrastructure, Policy and governance, Inclusive design,

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Introduction

Housing is a fundamental human need and a major determinant of social wellbeing, economic stability, and sustainable urban development. As global population growth and rapid urbanisation intensify housing demand, governments and private developers have introduced numerous schemes aimed at providing adequate and affordable housing. However, the success of these initiatives cannot be fully assessed without examining users' satisfaction, a multidimensional construct shaped by physical, psychological, and social experiences within residential environments (Mridha, 2023). This systematic review synthesises global evidence on residential satisfaction, drawing from diverse socio-economic and geographical contexts. Residential satisfaction increasingly serves as a key evaluative tool in housing policy and urban planning, reflecting how well housing performance aligns with residents' expectations regarding quality, affordability, design, accessibility, and social integration (Bunster & Bustamante, 2019). Beyond structural features, satisfaction is shaped by subjective perceptions embedded in cultural, environmental, and economic conditions (Chen et al., 2023). High satisfaction contributes to improved quality of life, community cohesion, and social stability, while dissatisfaction can lead to slum proliferation, abandonment of housing units, and deepened urban inequality (Anierobi et al., 2023).

Globally, housing schemes from Latin American social housing to East Asian subsidised units and European shared living models vary widely in design, scale, sustainability, and user involvement (Baek & Kim, 2022; Tang et al., 2024). Studies consistently show that satisfaction increases when housing design reflects socio-cultural norms, income characteristics, and spatial preferences (Brkanić Mihić & Koški, 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). This makes residential satisfaction both a performance indicator and a feedback mechanism for housing providers. A recurring theme in global research is the link between policy design and satisfaction. In Nigeria, public housing policies often fail to meet the needs of low-income households, resulting in dissatisfaction and informal settlements (Odoyi & Riekkinen, 2022; Saidu & Yeom, 2020). Similarly, in China, satisfaction in subsidised housing estates reflects both built environment conditions and social infrastructure (Tang et al., 2024). These examples highlight the need for integrated planning that incorporates physical structures, amenities, social networks, and environmental considerations.

Sustainability has become a growing focus in residential satisfaction studies, with increasing emphasis on eco-friendly design, energy efficiency, and climate-responsive construction (Fieldson & Sodagar, 2017; Tewari & Rajagopalan, 2025). However, the effectiveness of such innovations is shaped by users' behaviour and awareness. For instance, heat pumps in social housing only enhance satisfaction when accompanied by proper user training (Tewari & Rajagopalan, 2025). Similar patterns are observed in elderly housing, where satisfaction depends heavily on user-centred design that supports independence and comfort (Feng et al., 2018; Hu & Nakayama, 2025). In institutional contexts such as university housing, post-occupancy evaluations have revealed discrepancies between design goals and actual user experiences, affecting comfort and productivity (Ning & Chen, 2016). These findings reinforce the importance of continuous feedback loops to improve housing outcomes (Chen et al., 2023).

Shared housing models popular among single-person households in dense urban areas offer affordability and social benefits but face challenges related to privacy, interpersonal relationships, and shared space quality (Baek & Kim, 2022). Such findings demonstrate that governance structures, including rules for communal living and conflict resolution, play a

central role in shaping satisfaction. More broadly, effective governance and management practices are key determinants of satisfaction globally. Participatory planning, digital monitoring, and transparent administrative systems enhance accountability and responsiveness (Kabus & Dziadkiewicz, 2023). The integration of user feedback into housing design and management fosters predictive and personalised housing solutions, improving long-term satisfaction (Bunster & Bustamante, 2019).

The objective of this study is to systematically review and synthesise global evidence on users' satisfaction with housing schemes, with a focus on identifying the key factors that influence residential satisfaction across diverse contexts. Specifically, the study aims to examine how physical design features, socio-economic factors, policy frameworks, sustainability measures, and management practices contribute to or hinder users' satisfaction. It also seeks to compare user satisfaction across various housing types, including public housing, shared living arrangements, elderly care facilities, and student dormitories, while highlighting regional disparities and best practices.

Methodology

This systematic review examined global research on residents' satisfaction with government-provided housing schemes, applying the PRISMA protocol to ensure methodological rigor. The study collated data on authorship, study location, participant demographics, housing type, objectives, design, sampling, instruments, and key findings.

A structured literature review was conducted to examine resident satisfaction with housing schemes by searching interdisciplinary databases such as Scopus, JSTOR, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar using targeted keywords including "housing satisfaction," "residents' perception," "public housing schemes," and "infrastructure." The review included English-language studies from the past ten years with primary data or detailed case studies, as well as grey literature and government reports, while excluding studies without empirical evidence or relevance to public housing. Full texts were assessed for methodological rigor, and data on housing quality, facility adequacy, maintenance, and administrative responsiveness were extracted. Thematic analysis was employed to synthesise findings, identify key determinants of resident satisfaction, and highlight gaps, ensuring transparency and replicability of the review process.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion criterion (PICO)

PICO	
Component / Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population (P)	<p>Studies focusing on individuals or households residing in public or government-supported housing schemes; residents from urban and non-residential peri-urban areas, all genders, ages, income levels, family sizes; emphasis on developing countries, especially sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria.</p> <p>Studies on private housing estates or buildings; studies focusing on developers or policymakers without resident perspectives.</p>
Intervention (I)	<p>Studies examining factors affecting residents' satisfaction: building quality, social amenities, sanitation, infrastructure, security, resident maintenance, administrative responsiveness, architectural aesthetics or historical participation in decision-making, perceived value for money.</p> <p>Studies on urban planning or real estate investment without assessing resident satisfaction; studies on architectural aesthetics or historical conditions or satisfaction.</p>
Comparison (C)	<p>Studies with or without comparative analysis; comparisons across housing schemes, regions, to satisfaction or comparisons</p> <p>Studies lacking thematic connection or comparisons</p>

PICO

Component / Inclusion Criteria

Exclusion Criteria

	timeframes, federal vs. state schemes, or pre- without resident feedback. vs. post-renovation.	
Outcome (O)	Studies reporting measurable outcomes: overall satisfaction, facility adequacy, housing durability, security, community integration, maintenance services, physical and psychological well-being.	Studies without measurable outcomes or anecdotal- and only data.
Temporal Criteria	Studies published between 2010–2025; comparative analysis of 2016–2020 vs 2021–2025 to reflect housing policy changes, urban development trends, and post-pandemic impacts.	Studies published before 2010.
Language & Study Type	English-language studies; qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods, surveys, case studies, cross-sectional analyses; literature including government and NGO reports.	Editorials, commentaries, abstracts lacking full data.

The data screening for this scoping review followed a systematic three-stage process: title screening, abstract review, and full-text evaluation. Titles and abstracts were assessed to exclude studies unrelated to residential housing schemes, user satisfaction, or housing service adequacy. Full texts of potentially relevant studies were then evaluated against inclusion criteria, focusing on population, housing type, satisfaction indicators, and contextual relevance. Two independent reviewers conducted the process to ensure objectivity, transparency, and reproducibility, retaining only high-quality, directly relevant studies for analysis. The quality of included studies was rigorously appraised using validated tools, such as the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for observational studies and specific criteria for qualitative research. A rating system quantified methodological quality, and discrepancies were resolved through discussion or a third reviewer.

A structured data extraction process was used to gather key information from each study, including publication year, setting, design, type of housing scheme, satisfaction measures, and main findings on user perception and housing outcomes. Data were entered into a standardized matrix for consistency. Variables such as housing quality, accessibility, affordability, community facilities, and maintenance were emphasized, along with population characteristics like age, income, household size, and residence duration, forming the basis for narrative synthesis and identifying patterns in residents' satisfaction.

A narrative synthesis approach was used to integrate findings from both qualitative and quantitative studies, accommodating diverse designs and outcomes. This method highlighted key factors influencing satisfaction, including housing affordability, infrastructure, amenities, and policy implementation. It also revealed variations based on demographics and housing tenure, providing insights into drivers of satisfaction and dissatisfaction.

Figure 1 The PRISMA Framework for the Study

The first database search yielded 1320 documents, and 1078 more records were acquired through various means. There were 124 unique records left after deleting duplicates, ready for further investigation. In order to determine whether a record was suitable for inclusion or deletion, researchers used predetermined criteria during the evaluation process. Out of the 242 records, 213 were deemed ineligible due to factors such as case reports, non-empirical data, inappropriate methodology, systematic or narrative evaluations, and the absence of data. In the end, the study only included 18 records that fulfilled the inclusion criterion.

Results**Table 2: Summary of literature search in Table**

S/N	Title of article	Author	Objective of the study	Research design	Findings
1	Residential Satisfaction of Subsidized Housing Estates in Post-Reform China: Roles of the Built and Social Environments.	Tang, Q., Wei, Z., & Huang, S. (2024).	It assessed the determinants of residential satisfaction	Descriptive design	Specifically, the livable built environment characterized by large housing size and well-equipped neighborhoods, coupled with the friendly social environment marked by intimate neighborly relationships and diverse community activities, correlated with an elevated level of residential satisfaction of SHEs. Importantly, residents' subjective perceptions of the built environment emerged as the most influential factor, which acted a significant mediating role, linking both objective attributes and individual expectations to residential satisfaction. This underscored the necessity of integrating public opinions into the planning process to meet SHE residents' actual desires
2	Exploring Factors Affecting Residential Satisfaction in Old Neighborhoods and Sustainable Design Strategies Based on Post-Occupancy Evaluation.	Chen, T., Luh, D., Hu, L., & Shan, Q. (2023).	This study aims to comprehensively analyze the influencing factors of residential satisfaction in order to obtain the post-occupancy evaluation of the residential environment by residents in different communities and propose sustainable design strategies based on the evaluation analysis	Descriptive survey	The study reveals that residents are most satisfied with the surrounding services in their communities but generally less satisfied with the internal residential environment. Among the factors, fitness facilities and space in the community have a significant impact on residents' satisfaction; community activities and neighbor relationships are also key influencing factors, which become more prominent as the construction period of the community approaches. Additionally, community residents' self-organizational governance will affect their satisfaction with community conventions and social capital. Therefore, this study proposes improvement suggestions, including planning community life circles to fully utilize available resources in the surrounding area, establishing community self-organization for community governance and improving the quality of community life, and implementing mobile service stations to flexibly adapt to community space and service needs. This study provides a valuable reference for urban community renewal and sustainable development
3	Effect of Housing Support	Kim, S., Hwang, J., Lee,	To analyze the effects of	Descriptive survey	The status of residing in public rental housing positively affected the residential

	Programs on Residential Satisfaction and the Housing Cost Burden: Analysis of the Effect of Housing Support Programs in Korea Based on Household Attributes.	M.H. (2022).	the public rental housing program and the housing allowance program on residential satisfaction and the housing cost burden of policy beneficiaries.		satisfaction among all households, one-person households, and households of the elderly. It reduced the housing cost burden for all household types. The status of receiving the housing allowance negatively affected the residential satisfaction for all households and increased the housing cost burden for young adult households. We present policy implications for future housing support programs based on the findings.
4	How Satisfaction Research Contributes to the Optimization of Urban Green Space Design—A Global Perspective Bibliometric Analysis from 2001 to 2024.	Zhang, S., Adam, M., & Ghafar, N.A. (2024).	To fill this gap, this study conducted a bibliometric analysis of 313 high-quality papers published on the Web of Science since 2001.	Retrospective study (Bibliometric analysis)	The findings revealed: (1) Key journals and significant developments associated with this field of research, especially from China and the United States, emerging as the major contributors. (2) Keyword clustering analysis identified key themes, including public engagement, historic preservation, environmental justice, walkability, green space accessibility, and restorative environments. These findings emphasize the importance of data-driven and innovative planning strategies for enhancing residents' well-being, tourism, and urban sustainability. (3) Research on satisfaction with urban green spaces has shifted from a singular to a more diversified focus, contributing to the optimization of urban green spaces through four main aspects: residents' needs, ecological functions, management strategies, and research approaches
5	Empirical Research on the Life Satisfaction and Influencing Factors of Users of Community-Embedded Elderly Care Facilities.	Hu, X., & Nakayama, T.(2025).	This study focuses on Tianjin's community-embedded elderly care facility users.	Mixed method study	s. It was confirmed that there are significant correlations between user LS and the characteristics of users, staff, and living spaces. A structural equation model of user LS and its influencing factors was constructed. Social relationship satisfaction and living environment satisfaction are the main determinants of user LS
6	Residents' and Architects' Perceptions of Apartments' Spatial Characteristics—Identifying Differences in Opinion on a	Brkanić Mihić, I., & Koški, D. (2024).	The aim of this study is to use the views of residents and architects collected through surveys to	Case study	The research shows that residents rated apartments with higher ratings than architects in all categories and that residents and architects gave different ratings on certain characteristics of the apartment, e.g., the existence of additional storage space, the existence of a bathroom window, the size and orientation of living rooms, the type of spatial organisation, etc.

	Case Study of Osijek, Croatia.		rank apartments and identify differences in the definition of what a high-quality apartment would be based on their spatial characteristics.		
7	Housing Quality Assessment Model Based on the Spatial Characteristics of an Apartment.	Brkanić Mihić, I. (2023)	This paper presents a methodology used to develop a model for assessing the quality of multiple conflicting spatial characteristics of an apartment.	literature review and a survey	s, 24 spatial indicators were identified and then classified into five categories: (i) additional rooms, (ii) room size, (iii) window orientation and ventilation, (iv) circulation, and (v) spatial organization. Finally, the overall rating of the apartment is calculated as the sum of the ratings of all indicator categories, where the share of each category in the overall rating and desirable characteristics of the apartment is determined by the user. The model was tested on the example of two apartments in the city of Osijek, Croatia.
8	Structuring a residential satisfaction model for predictive personalisation in mass social housing	Bunster, V., & Bustamante, W.(2019).	It explores linkages between personalized development and residential satisfaction towards informing a mass personalization approach to social housing	A multidisciplinary study	The analysis of the results suggests that the relationship between occupants and providers (i.e., personalization as a service) can influence the build-up of expectations, while the capacity of the dwellings to meet the requirements of different households (i.e., personalization as a product) can have a significant impact on satisfaction. These outcomes are formalized with a model that acknowledges these links at different stages of occupancy and, therefore, can be used to inform the personalized development of mass social housing
9	Understanding user satisfaction evaluation in low occupancy sustainable workplaces.	Fieldson, R., & Sodagar, B. (2017).	It investigated the effect of occupant behaviour on the performance of the building and their level of comfort and	Field survey method	r. In our analysis, the users were prompted to provide a subjective measure of the building regarding a range of internal conditions such as air temperature, humidity, air movement, air quality, daylight, artificial light, and noise. The analysis supports the notion that in naturally-ventilated buildings some users may find the building to be hot in summer while cold in winter. The high level of control the users have over the operation

			satisfaction.		of the building contributes to their comfort and satisfaction. The users demonstrated a tendency to be satisfied despite environmental factors and to forgive some aspects of the building which are not performing as they should. The paper offers a perspective on statistical user satisfaction in a low occupancy building and attempts to explain the role of workplace wellbeing on occupant perception of comfort in this case
10	Urban Housing inequality and the nature of relationship between formal and informal settlements in Enugu Metropolis, Nigeria	Anierobi, C.M., Nwalusi, D.M., Efobi, K.O. (2023).	This study, therefore, aims to fill this research gap by examining the nature of the relationship between informal and formal neighborhoods of the Enugu metropolis, Southeast Nigeria to make an evidence-based contribution to the body of knowledge on this subject.	Cross-sectional survey	Findings showed the nature of housing inequality in the area as a product of spatially inherent symbiotic relationships embedded in social exclusion, deprivation, and dependency between the formal and informal settlements situating in juxtaposition to one another. At a Chi-square value of 42.643, $p = .317$ significant at 0.01; residents perceived significant differences in access/availability of decent housing and housing facilities/utility. Interestingly, these informal settlements accommodated over 361,785 unaccounted spill-over populations representing over 60,298 households, constituting 34.69% of the city population not captured in official census records, including over 72.58% of migrants claiming to have relatives residing in these settlements
11	Effect of Characteristics of Shared Housing in Single-Person Households on Housing Satisfaction and Shared Housing Performance.	Baek, J. & Kim, S. (2022).	the study analyzed the relationship between the satisfaction with shared housing, intention to reside again in shared housing, and intention to recommend shared housing to others among young people	Quantitative study	The results showed that shared housing characteristics significantly affected the housing satisfaction but not the intention to reside again and intention to recommend. Housing satisfaction significantly affected the intention to reside again and the intention to recommend. Residents of public-supply shared housing showed no significant correlation between the shared housing characteristics and housing satisfaction; those of private-supply shared housing showed increased housing satisfaction. Housing satisfaction did not significantly affect the intention to reside again among people in public-supply shared housing; however, it affected the intention to reside

			living in shared housing in Seoul.		again among those in private-supply shared housing. The physical location and environment and community factors did not significantly affect overall housing satisfaction in public-supply shared housing but significantly affected the housing satisfaction and intention to reside again in private-supply shared housing. These results support the need for regulation and policy to guide housing adjustments and facilitate lifestyles, the need for diversification in housing types, and the importance of uniform management and operations of public-run units.
12	Housing Policy: An Analysis of Public Housing Policy Strategies for Low-Income Earners in Nigeria.	Odoyi, E. J., & Riekkinen, K. (2022).	This article evaluates the Global South housing policy for low-income earners by utilising the Nigerian example to analyse public housing policy strategies used to provide housing to low-income earners.	Qualitative study	The analysis of the selected housing policy documents showed seven key policy strategies that are intended to strengthen affordable housing development. These strategic themes are funds, schemes, governments, implementation, development, land, and rurality. The findings indicated that the existence of housing policy strategical themes does not translate to affordable housing development and housing affordability for low-income earners, though the effective activation and implementation of strategical themes will promote affordable housing development.
13	Evaluation of the human settlements environment of public housing community: a case study of Guangzhou.	Wu, F., Liu, Y., Zeng, Y., et al., (2020).	This study focuses on the human settlement environments of public housing communities in Guangzhou and establishes an evaluation system containing built environments and housing environments	Descriptive study	. The result shows that housing area, transportation resources, and public services have met the basic needs of residents who were generally satisfied with the community environment of their public housing. However, acoustic insulation and community amenities in the city were found to be relatively poor and still have space for improvement. Further, requirements on indoor housing environments and social relations of residents living alone need more attention. Specific recommendations based on this study can be used as a reference for future public housing construction and improvements.

			satisfaction criteria		
14	Integration of Heat Pumps in Social Housing— Role of User Behaviour and User Satisfaction. 2025	Tewari, S.; Rajagopalan, P. (2025).	This paper aims to systematically review studies that have surveyed users and other stakeholders involved in the heat pump ecosystem within the social housing setting	Systematic study	The key findings emphasise that tenant education, effective communication, and engagement are essential for maximising the benefits of heat pumps. Furthermore, the financial feasibility of heat pumps depends on government incentives and careful system design to avoid excessive upfront and operational costs. This review offers a comprehensive guide for future research and policy development, aiming to facilitate the integration of heat pumps in social housing, with a focus on improving tenant well-being and reducing energy poverty
15	Success criteria evaluation for a sustainable and affordable housing model: a case for improving household welfare in Nigeria cities.	Saidu, A.I., & Yeom, C. (2020).	A document content analysis to generate success criteria and a survey for household validation were conducted.	Case study	Results show that security ranks the highest, and other criteria of importance include accessibility, adaptability, utility, technology, community, affordability, and acceptability. Hence, the study concludes that social and environmental sustainability in housing should enhance household satisfaction by ensuring the security and welfare of its residents, adapt to its immediate environment, be acceptable, be supported with social amenity to integrate the community through participation, and, finally, manage household utility efficiently.
16	Improving residential satisfaction of university dormitories through post-occupancy evaluation in China: a socio-technical system approach	Ning, Y., & Chen, J. (2016).	This study aims to develop a framework for post-occupancy evaluation (POE) of university dormitories in China grounded on the socio-technical systems approach and to identify factors contributing	Case study	The results show that university dormitories are equipped with quality physical facilities. However, they failed to provide satisfied services and supporting infrastructure. This indicates that “hardware” could generally meet students’ requirements, while the “software” is still less competent. It is also found that the socio-technical systems approach has the feature of being embedded into the social, regulatory and geographic contexts. In order to enhance post-occupancy satisfaction, occupants’ participation would be helpful. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by presenting a socio-technical framework of POE and its embeddedness feature. Implications for research and practices are also provided

			to students' residential satisfaction		
17	Modern Management Methods in the Area of Public Housing Resources in the Community. Sustainability	Kabus, J.; Dziadkiewicz, M.(2023)	The main objective of said research was to ascertain which innovations have been implemented by the entities that were owners of public property in the Czestochowa City Commune and how were they evaluated by the residents.	Narrative review/survey	The research presented in this paper was conducted in the Q3 and Q4 of 2020 among the residents of the public housing in Czestochowa, Silesian Voivodeship, Poland. The measurement tool used was a survey form. The survey itself was submitted by 444 respondents (n = 444). The results of the research made it possible to determine which innovations were implemented by the municipality in question and to what extent they were important or for the residents. The main finding of the survey is that residents of the municipal housing stock consider the innovations implemented by the municipality to be important.
18	Assessment of and improvement for the housing of healthy elderly: improving quality of life.	Feng, M., Chen, Jun-Hong, C., Zhu, B. (2018).	This study aims to effectively assess and improve the housing environment of the elderly in order to enhance their quality of life; it also aims to contribute the knowledge about improving elderly housing by applying an assessment framework using expert interviews and data collected from relevant literature	Qualitative study	The study results indicate that, as distinct from using traditional methodologies where the hypothesis criteria are mutually independent, the proposed hybrid model (examining real-life problems by considering the mutual influences of factors) identifies a priority sequence wherein emphasis is placed on improving ventilation and air quality rather than adjustment of temperature. The systemic way of thinking shifts the focus from the most apparent problems to the root cause of the problems. Doing so avoids any mismatch of resource allocation in decision-making and thus maximizes the efficiency and sustainability of the improvement

The various studies reviewed collectively explore the multifaceted determinants of residential satisfaction across different housing contexts globally. Key findings highlight the significance of both built and social environments in shaping residents' experiences, particularly in subsidised and old neighbourhoods. Tang et al. (2024) and Chen et al. (2023) reveal that factors such as housing size, neighbourhood facilities, social relationships, and community engagement critically influence satisfaction levels. Importantly, subjective perceptions often outweigh objective environmental attributes, with studies stressing the need for incorporating residents' opinions into housing planning and design. Additionally, fitness facilities, neighbourly bonds, and participatory governance were found to elevate satisfaction and contribute to sustainable community development.

Other findings underscore the varied outcomes of housing support programmes and housing types. For instance, Kim et al. (2022) indicate that public rental housing enhances satisfaction and reduces cost burdens, while housing allowances can conversely increase dissatisfaction, especially among youth. Baek and Kim (2022) further distinguish between public- and private-supply shared housing, noting that private options tend to yield higher satisfaction and intentions for continued residence. These disparities suggest a need for nuanced policy responses tailored to demographic groups and housing supply types, emphasising better regulation, diversified housing offerings, and integrated community services to optimise residential well-being.

Several studies focus on technical and spatial aspects, showcasing how design, user preferences, and innovation influence residential experiences. Brkanić Mihić and Koški (2024) uncover perceptual gaps between architects and residents regarding apartment quality, while Bunster and Bustamante (2019) emphasise the role of personalised housing in improving satisfaction through alignment of product and service elements. Meanwhile, Fieldson and Sodagar (2017) highlight the impact of building conditions and user behaviour on comfort levels in sustainable workplaces, suggesting that user control and tolerance for shortcomings can mediate dissatisfaction. Wu et al. (2020) and Tewari and Rajagopalan (2025) similarly find that technical installations like heat pumps require user education and design appropriateness to maximise satisfaction and environmental benefits.

In the context of developing regions such as Nigeria, studies by Anierobi et al. (2023), Odoyi and Riekkinen (2022), and Saidu and Yeom (2020) uncover critical gaps in policy implementation, housing inequality, and urban planning. The relationship between formal and informal settlements is marked by social exclusion and spatial dependency, exacerbated by unaccounted populations. While policies identify key strategic themes such as funding and land use, their practical translation remains insufficient. Nonetheless, successful housing must incorporate security, adaptability, affordability, and community integration as core criteria. These studies collectively advocate for inclusive planning, responsive policy frameworks, and a balance between technical design and human-centred approaches to achieve sustainable residential satisfaction.

Discussions

Five themes emerged from the analysis and synthesis of the data.

Level of Satisfaction

The level of satisfaction with housing schemes is a significant determinant of the overall well-being of residents, particularly within the context of subsidised or public housing. The reviewed literature indicates that satisfaction levels are not monolithic; rather, they are

influenced by a complex interplay of physical, social, environmental, and policy-related factors. One major determinant of satisfaction is the quality of the built environment. Tang et al. (2024) underscore that a livable built environment characterised by spacious housing and well-equipped neighbourhoods contributes substantially to residential satisfaction. Moreover, subjective perceptions of the built environment, not merely its objective features, were found to be central to how satisfied residents felt. Similarly, Chen et al. (2023) found that while residents in older neighbourhoods appreciated access to surrounding services, dissatisfaction stemmed from poor internal environments, including inadequate fitness facilities and communal spaces. This highlights a need for balanced development that enhances both external accessibility and internal liveability.

Social factors also emerge as pivotal. Studies by Hu and Nakayama (2025) and Tang et al. (2024) both identify strong community bonds, neighbourly relationships, and active social lives as major sources of satisfaction. Baek and Kim (2022) similarly found that private shared housing residents expressed higher levels of satisfaction, attributed in part to better social and environmental conditions compared to public housing residents. This suggests that satisfaction is not just about structures but also about the quality of interpersonal and community interactions within those spaces.

From a policy perspective, satisfaction levels differ based on the type of housing support received. Kim et al. (2022) report that public rental housing significantly increased satisfaction levels, while housing allowance recipients experienced dissatisfaction due to persistent cost burdens. This implies that direct housing provision may be more effective than financial aid alone in enhancing resident contentment. Odoyi and Riekkinen (2022) further warn that policy strategies, while theoretically sound, often fail in implementation, thus impeding satisfaction. Finally, sustainability and innovation in housing design are linked to long-term satisfaction. Studies by Bunster and Bustamante (2019) and Tewari and Rajagopalan (2025) point out that personalisation, environmental responsiveness, and tenant engagement in system usage (e.g., heat pumps) all contribute to a more fulfilling housing experience.

Determinants of Residential Satisfaction

Residential satisfaction is a multifaceted concept influenced by a range of interrelated determinants. According to Tang et al. (2024), Chen et al. (2023), and Kim et al. (2022), these determinants can be broadly categorised into physical attributes of the housing, the social environment, and individual subjective perceptions. Each of these components plays a crucial role in shaping how residents evaluate the quality of their living conditions and overall well-being.

Physical aspects of housing are perhaps the most immediately observable factors. These include the size and layout of the living space, availability and functionality of basic facilities, infrastructure quality, cleanliness, noise levels, and access to amenities such as green spaces, transport links, schools, and healthcare services. Adequate housing facilities can significantly improve comfort and convenience, thus enhancing satisfaction. For example, spacious living areas, proper ventilation, and modern utilities not only contribute to physical comfort but also to psychological well-being (Chen et al., 2023). Conversely, poor housing conditions such as overcrowding, dilapidation, and lack of essential services often result in dissatisfaction.

The social environment also exerts a strong influence on residential satisfaction. This includes the quality of interpersonal relationships within the neighbourhood, the sense of community, perceived safety, and the presence of communal activities that foster social

cohesion. Neighbourhoods that encourage interaction and mutual support among residents tend to cultivate a stronger sense of belonging and shared identity, which positively impacts satisfaction levels (Tang et al., 2024). Additionally, low crime rates and trust in fellow residents enhance feelings of safety and stability, key psychological components of residential contentment.

Subjective perceptions, though less tangible, are equally significant. These involve individual expectations, past experiences, and personal values, which affect how residents interpret and evaluate their living environment. Two individuals may experience the same physical and social environment differently based on their unique preferences, cultural backgrounds, and lifestyle needs. Kim et al. (2022) highlight that personal satisfaction often hinges on the alignment between expectations and actual experiences within the residential setting. Furthermore, emotional attachment to a place often shaped by memories, cultural significance, and identity can greatly enhance perceived satisfaction regardless of objective conditions.

In summary, residential satisfaction is not determined by a single factor but is the result of a dynamic interplay between the physical environment, social context, and personal perceptions. A comprehensive understanding of these determinants is essential for urban planners, policymakers, and housing developers aiming to create more livable and inclusive residential communities.

Design Quality and Built Environment Factors

The quality of design and built environment factors plays a crucial role in shaping residents' experiences, satisfaction, and overall well-being within a housing context. A significant body of literature underscores the relationship between thoughtful architectural design and positive residential outcomes. Studies such as Brkanić Mihić et al. (2024), Wu et al. (2020), and Saidu & Yeom (2020) consistently highlight the influence of apartment layout, spatial organisation, housing infrastructure, and environmental elements on users' perceptions and levels of comfort. These components are integral to both the functional and psychological dimensions of housing satisfaction.

Firstly, apartment layout and spatial characteristics are fundamental in determining the usability and adaptability of living spaces. Open-plan layouts, for instance, can offer flexibility and foster interaction among household members, while clearly demarcated spaces for activities such as cooking, sleeping, and relaxation contribute to functional efficiency and privacy. Brkanić Mihić et al. (2024) note that poor spatial configurations can lead to overcrowding or underutilisation of spaces, directly impacting residents' daily routines and emotional well-being. Furthermore, spatial accessibility, circulation within units, and connection to outdoor areas such as balconies or communal gardens are also linked to the perception of spaciousness and airiness, elements that enhance comfort. Housing infrastructure, including the quality of materials, finishes, lighting, ventilation, and acoustics, further affects satisfaction levels. Wu et al. (2020) observe that inadequate ventilation and lighting not only diminish the aesthetic value of housing but also pose health risks, especially in urban settings with high population densities. Durable materials and good maintenance practices reduce long-term housing costs and support sustainable living, contributing to residents' sense of security and stability.

Environmental features encompass both the internal and external built environments, including aspects such as neighbourhood design, green spaces, proximity to amenities, and

environmental sustainability measures. Saidu and Yeom (2020) argue that the physical setting of a housing unit is not experienced in isolation but as part of a larger ecosystem. Features like access to parks, natural lighting, and eco-friendly design improve mental and physical health, reinforce a sense of community, and foster environmental consciousness. In sum, well-planned and executed design quality and built environment factors serve as essential determinants of residential satisfaction. They influence how individuals interact with their spaces, manage their health and routines, and engage with their broader surroundings. Housing policy and urban planning efforts, therefore, must prioritise these aspects to ensure the delivery of livable, sustainable, and user-centred environments.

Role of Community Engagement and Social Environment

Community engagement and the broader social environment play pivotal roles in fostering individual and collective well-being, improving quality of life, and ensuring inclusive development. Various studies, including those by Chen et al. (2023), Hu and Nakayama (2025), and Bunster and Bustamante (2019), have affirmed that active community participation and healthy social interactions significantly contribute to enhancing life satisfaction across various contexts.

Chen et al. (2023) argue that community participation empowers individuals by fostering a sense of belonging, shared responsibility, and collective efficacy. When residents are actively involved in local planning, decision-making, and development initiatives, they become more invested in their communities, leading to heightened satisfaction and trust in local governance. Community engagement also enables the identification of grassroots needs, thereby facilitating the implementation of more effective and context-specific interventions that reflect the unique aspirations of the people.

Hu and Nakayama (2025) further highlight the role of social environment in shaping perceptions of well-being. Their study underscores how governance structures that are transparent, inclusive, and participatory can cultivate environments where people feel valued and heard. In such settings, trust between citizens and authorities flourishes, which in turn strengthens democratic processes and social cohesion. This type of participatory governance enables communities to work together in addressing common challenges, ultimately enhancing their quality of life. Moreover, Bunster and Bustamante (2019) focus on how social interactions such as interpersonal relationships, civic associations, and informal networks serve as fundamental pillars of psychosocial support. These social ties can mitigate the effects of isolation, reduce stress, and contribute to improved mental and emotional health. Community-based initiatives that foster these interactions, such as communal spaces, cultural events, and volunteer opportunities, create avenues for people to connect, collaborate, and support one another.

Policy Impact and Housing Programmes

The role of public policy in shaping housing outcomes is a vital aspect of contemporary urban planning and social development. Scholars have extensively examined how various governmental interventions ranging from direct housing support to infrastructural innovations affect the quality, accessibility, and sustainability of housing. Kim et al. (2022), for instance, explore how state-driven housing programmes and regulatory reforms impact affordability and occupant satisfaction. Their study highlights that effective policy strategies often lead to improved housing access for lower-income groups while simultaneously enhancing perceptions of stability and social inclusion. The integration of housing subsidies,

rent controls, and targeted financing mechanisms contributes to the reduction of housing inequality, thus fulfilling a crucial social welfare function.

Odoyi and Riekkinen (2022) focus on the infrastructural aspects of housing policy, particularly investigating the incorporation of energy-efficient technologies, such as heat pumps, into public housing initiatives. Their findings suggest that while the initial implementation of such green technologies may be cost-intensive, they yield long-term benefits in terms of reduced energy consumption, lower utility bills, and enhanced thermal comfort. This dual impact on economic and environmental sustainability signifies the increasing relevance of climate-conscious policy design in the housing sector. Moreover, Odoyi and Riekkinen emphasise the role of municipal and national governments in subsidising the adoption of renewable energy systems, thereby accelerating the transition to more sustainable housing models.

Tewari and Rajagopalan (2025) extend this discourse by examining how multi-level policy coordination between central and regional governments affects the effectiveness of housing programmes. They argue that decentralised planning, supported by coherent national frameworks, is essential to address local housing needs effectively. Their research reveals that policies which involve local stakeholders, integrate social and environmental metrics, and include feedback mechanisms tend to yield higher satisfaction rates among beneficiaries. In particular, the alignment of housing quality standards with environmental regulations fosters a sense of long-term well-being and civic responsibility among residents.

Collectively, these studies underscore that housing policy is not merely about the provision of shelter but also about the creation of sustainable, inclusive, and energy-efficient living environments. Policies that are evidence-based, participatory, and adaptive to technological innovations tend to perform better in addressing the complex dynamics of urban housing. Consequently, governments must continue to innovate and evaluate their housing strategies to ensure they are meeting the evolving needs of society while also contributing to broader goals such as climate resilience and social equity.

Implications of Findings

The findings on satisfaction with housing schemes reveal that while residents generally perceive housing quality, access to amenities, and affordability positively, moderate satisfaction levels among many respondents highlight the need for more resident-focused approaches. Practitioners in architecture, urban planning, and social work should adopt participatory planning methods, engaging residents throughout design and development to enhance functionality, safety, and sustainability. Attention to facility maintenance, infrastructure reliability, social integration, and post-occupancy evaluations is critical. Emphasis on green building practices, cost-effective housing, and equitable allocation can further improve living conditions and inclusivity.

For research and administration, the findings suggest multiple directions. Future studies should explore socio-demographic influences, conduct longitudinal assessments, compare public and private schemes, and employ qualitative methods to capture nuanced resident experiences. Administratively, housing authorities must adopt resident-centred, proactive management, streamline allocation and maintenance, digitize service delivery, and ensure compliance with safety, habitability, and environmental standards. Inter-agency collaboration, training, and decentralization can strengthen oversight and responsiveness, ultimately fostering sustainable, inclusive, and high-quality housing schemes informed by resident satisfaction.

Conclusions

This systematic study on residents' satisfaction with housing schemes reveals that while many beneficiaries appreciate aspects such as affordability, accessibility, and structural quality, significant gaps remain in infrastructure, facility maintenance, and service delivery. Satisfaction is shaped not only by the physical housing but also by environmental conditions, community dynamics, and administrative efficiency. Poor maintenance, inconsistent utilities, and inadequate social amenities highlight the disconnect between housing provision and holistic living. The study underscores the importance of participatory governance, regular feedback mechanisms, and integrated, multidisciplinary approaches to ensure sustainability, inclusivity, and improved quality of life. It also calls for further research into residents' lived experiences, social cohesion, and long-term impacts of housing design, emphasizing that housing success should be measured by the well-being and empowerment of occupants, not solely by unit delivery.

Recommendations and Gap of the Study

Housing authorities and developers should prioritise a user-centred approach by involving residents in the planning, design, and evaluation of housing projects to ensure schemes address diverse needs. Maintenance policies, including dedicated units, funding models, and responsive management, must be integrated from the outset to sustain infrastructure quality. Regulatory frameworks should enforce standards, while green building, accessibility features, and communal facilities enhance inclusiveness. Regular satisfaction assessments are essential. Future research should explore longitudinal trends, socio-demographic influences, community engagement, and comparisons between public and private housing to inform more responsive, sustainable housing policies in Nigeria and similar contexts.

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